

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT
ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART III. COMPARATIVE STUDIES
UNDER THE VISIBLE AND THE QUARTZ ULTRAVIOLET

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The Joshi effect Δi has been observed in pure oxygen (250 mm.) enclosed in a Siemens' tube with a quartz window for end on irradiation, and excited by 2 to 5 kV of 50 cycles frequency. Δi is greater in Hg light (29.2%) than under a (glass) incandescent bulb (16.9%), and is reduced to the latter when the ultraviolet is cut off.

That the magnitude of the Joshi effect Δi in chlorine increases from the infra-red to the ultraviolet, *i.e.*, frequency-wise, has been observed by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75; *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 317). The author and Kamath (Part II, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 467) have shown that Δi in oxygen under the visible is greater in the blue than in the green red. The results of a preliminary investigation of the author (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1948, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No 35) having revealed that Δi in oxygen is greater under the total radiations from a quartz mercury vapour lamp than under the visible, it was of interest to study in some detail the production of the effect Δi in oxygen under the ultraviolet.

EXPERIMENTAL

The discharge vessel consisted of a Siemens' all-glass ozoniser which had a quartz window cemented on one end. It was filled with purified oxygen at 250 mm. (25°) pressure, and excited by potentials V of 50 cycles frequency varied over 2 to 5 kV (r. m. s.). A Cambridge vacuo-junction was used as the A. C. indicator. The inner

TABLE I

Comparative studies of the Joshi effect in oxygen under the visible and the quartz ultraviolet.

$pO_2 = 250$ mm. (25°). Temperature = 25°. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec. Detector = Vacuo-junction. Sources of irradiation = Quartz mercury vapour lamp and 200 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulb, 15 cm. from the ozoniser

Irradiation parallel to the axis of the ozoniser

V in kilo- volts (r. m. s.)	Quartz mercury vapour lamp											
	Quartz window				Quartz window & glass plate				200 Volt, 200 watt (glass) bulb			
	i_0 .	i_L .	Δi .	% Δi .	i_0 .	Δi .	% Δi .	i_0 .	Δi .	% Δi .		
2.67	5.1	3.61	1.49	29.2	4.12	0.98	19.2	4.24	0.86	16.9		
2.93	7.14	5.48	1.66	23.3	6.16	0.98	13.7	6.25	0.89	12.5		
3.2	9.59	7.94	1.65	17.2	8.60	0.99	10.3	8.72	0.87	8.9		
3.47	11.40	9.7	1.70	14.9	10.3	1.1	9.6	10.40	1.00	8.8		
3.73	12.49	10.73	1.76	14.1	11.23	1.26	10.1	11.40	1.09	8.7		
4	13.19	11.32	1.87	14.2	12.17	1.02	7.7	12.37	0.82	6.2		
4.27	13.96	12.13	1.83	13.1	13.04	0.92	6.6	13.23	0.73	5.2		

tube of the ozoniser was filled with a concentrated solution of potassium permanganate which served to absorb all light; the ozoniser was also wrapped in black paper, except at the quartz window, to screen against external light. Current observations were made at different V in dark; when irradiated through the quartz window, in the end-on position, with a quartz mercury vapour lamp, when the ultraviolet portion of the above radiations was cut off appreciably by the superposition of a 2 mm. glass plate over the quartz, and with a 200 volt, 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulb placed in the position of the mercury lamp. In Table I is recorded but one typical set of observations.

D I S C U S S I O N

The foregoing results show that despite restricted irradiation, Δi in oxygen under the ultraviolet is appreciable, being as high as 29.2% current-decrease at 2.67 kV; this is indicative of the large magnitude of the Joshi effect that can be produced under favourable conditions. The values of both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ for the quartz mercury vapour lamp and only the quartz window are higher than those obtained with the 200 volt, 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulb. Thus *e. g.*, at the above V , whilst Δi and $\% \Delta i$ are respectively 1.49 and 29.2 with total radiations from the mercury lamp, the corresponding values with the bulb are 0.86 and 16.9. Further, the effect due to the mercury lamp is reduced markedly on the addition of a 2 mm. thick glass plate over the quartz window, the values for Δi and $\% \Delta i$ thus obtained being sensibly similar to those observed under visible light. Thus, at the above V , $\% \Delta i$ is 29.2 without, and 19.2 with the glass plate; that with the incandescent (glass) bulb is 16.9. It is known that variation in Δi due to intensity fluctuations is not appreciable at high light-intensities, as long as the effective mean frequency is not altered (Joshi, *loc. cit.* Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*). It follows therefore that the relatively high magnitude of the effect under irradiation with the mercury lamp and only through the quartz window may be attributed to the high frequencies in the radiations, and not so much to their greater over-all intensity compared with those from the bulb.

Oxygen has a number of absorption bands in the ultraviolet (Liveing and Dewar, *Phil. Mag.*, 1888, **26**, 286; Lyman, *Astrophys. J.*, 1908, **27**, 87; Wartenberg, *Physikal. Z.*, 1910, **11**, 1168; L. and E. Bloch, *Compt. rend.*, 1914, **158**, 1161; Duclaux and Jeantet, *ibid.*, 1921, **173**, 581; Shaver, *Trans. Roy. Soc. Canada*, 1921, **15**, 7; Füchtbauer and Holm, *Physikal. Z.*, 1925, **26**, 345; Schmidt, *Z. Physik*, 1925, **31**, 475; Leifson, *Astrophys. J.*, 1926, **63**, 73; Dufay, *Compt. rend.*, 1929, **188**, 162; Granath, *Phys. Rev.*, 1929, **34**, 1045). In view of the fact, however, that despite absorption in the green and the red, Δi in oxygen for these wave-bands is but small (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*), it is unlikely, as has been postulated by Joshi (*loc. cit.*), that the effect Δi is a consequence of selective light absorption.

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